

D6.2

Second Policy Brief

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to 28/02/2025*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AAKS	Filmyby Aarhus
AROS	Aarhus Kunstmuseum
AU	Aarhus University
AUAS	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
BS	Battlesheep
CBC	Fonden Creative Business Cup
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CI	Creative Industries
CMO	Obidos Municipal Council
DM	Dropstuff Media
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
KEA	KEA European Affairs
MEET	MEET Digital Communication
NISV	The Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision
RI	Research Institutions
RT	Roundtable
UL	Lusófona University
WP	Work Package
QH	Quadruple Helix Ecosystem
UN	United Nations
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

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Table of Contents

<i>Technical References</i>	2
<i>Document History</i>	3
<i>Acronyms and Abbreviations</i>	4
<i>Disclaimer</i>	4
<i>Summary of Project and Deliverable</i>	7
<i>Introduction</i>	10
1 <i>Summary of the first EPIC-WE roundtable and policy brief</i>	12
2 <i>Methodology and Preparation</i>	14
3 <i>Preparatory Work for Second Roundtables</i>	15
3.1 <i>Research Overview</i>	15
3.1.1 <i>Capacity Building Session on “Policy-Making in CClIs”</i>	15
3.1.2 <i>Other efforts and resources</i>	15
3.1.3 <i>Key Findings and Research Results</i>	19
4 <i>Second Roundtable Session</i>	24
4.1 <i>Internal Participant Profile</i>	25
4.2 <i>External Participant Profile</i>	27
4.3 <i>Questions & Key Discussions</i>	27
5 <i>Policy Recommendations</i>	31
6 <i>Next Roundtables</i>	36
7 <i>Conclusion</i>	37
<i>Bibliography</i>	38
<i>Appendices</i>	40

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Summary of policy recommendations 12

Figure 2: Summary of policy recommendations 13

Figure 3: Summary of D6.1 13

Figure 4: Planning of the roundtables and deliverable 14

Figure 5: Employment statistics by gender in design industry 23

Figure 6: Screenshot from the policy roundtable session - 1..... 24

Figure 7: Screenshots from the policy roundtable session - 2..... 25

Summary of Deliverable

Summary of Project and Deliverable

EPIC-WE introduces cultural hubs, cultural game jams, culture- and value-sensitive game-making and games through and for culture as a novel approach to empower young people as co-creators of European culture and shapers of their own futures in society, cultural institutions (CHIs) and creative industries (CIs). The backbone of the project is the EPIC-WE quadruple helix cultural innovation ecosystem and cultural hubs - a transferable framework where youth, CHIs, CIs and higher education institutions (HEIs) cooperate and co-create as partners within the ecosystem. Together, EPIC-WE partners engage in cultural game jams to create games through and for culture inspired by cultural heritage and cultural or societal issues. The model and framework explore the potential of this approach as a method for strengthening European values, identities, belonging, and cultural participation. Through game-making activities, EPIC-WE will equip youth with cultural-creative imagination and competencies to face cultural/societal issues and ideas with curiosity, creativity, agency and imagination – what we call Empowered Participation.

The project is carried out as an ambitious 3-year Design-Based Research and Innovation (DBR) action across three European sites, where the EPIC-WE ecosystem actors collaborate and, through this, develop, implement and evaluate the proposed model and framework. The validated DBR innovations are presented as accessible and usable resources that enable CI, CHI, HEI, and youth across Europe to replicate the EPIC-WE ecosystem and its activities and methods. Through extensive research, capacity building and policy advocacy activities, EPIC-WE will ensure that the project's results reach a wide range of European CHI, CI and HEI actors, including the game industry, civil society organisations and youth. The consortium is a quadruple helix ecosystem, bringing together leading research, cultural and creative sector organisations with multidisciplinary excellence in DBR, participatory and value-sensitive design, game design, cultural participation, and youth engagement to empower youth as future culture-makers and game-makers in CHIs, CIs and HEIs and as value-sensitive agents of change in society.

For this purpose, the project has four identified objectives as follows:

OBJECTIVE 1: ASSESS. Explore the potential of games and game-making practices to empower youth and contribute to the strengthening of European values and cultural participation.

OBJECTIVE 2: INNOVATE. Develop and validate a framework for cultural game jams in quadruple helix ecosystems.

OBJECTIVE 3: TRANSFER. Produce accessible resources that enable organisations to replicate the quadruple helix game-making ecosystem across Europe.

OBJECTIVE 4: SCALE. Equip quadruple helix actors with knowledge, skills and policy instruments to exploit the potential of game-making with youth for the benefit of European society.

The WP6, under which D6.2 is included, mainly contributes to O4 SCALE with combined support from the other tasks and deliverables of the WP. The primary goal of this work package is to ensure the accurate and meaningful measurement of impact while providing adequate tools for future engagement with the projects developed core results: 1) the EPIC-WE cultural innovation ecosystems, 2) quadruple helix cultural hubs, 3) cultural game jams (CGJs) that position game-making as a form of culture-making, and 4) their accompanying CGJ Kit supporting youth in the creation of games through and for culture. Also, it aims to offer capacity-building opportunities and policy recommendations for CI, CHIs, and HEIs. Finally, this WP establishes a robust connection to stakeholders and policymakers by engaging them in a collaborative and co-creative three-step policy development process.

Towards this end, the policy recommendations support the EPIC-WE project's core results combined with other deliverables under the WP as a whole, bringing together stakeholders in a co-creation atmosphere to facilitate the exchange of opinions, guided strategic discussions and provide input for future endeavours to drive positive cultural and societal change within the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, QH Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams.

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

EPIC-WE's outcomes will include a validated framework of cultural ecosystems for QH Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) enacted through transformative and equal partnerships between youth, CHIs, CIs, and HEIs, providing results, methods, tools, and recommendations for policymakers. The policy briefs support establishing this framework by ensuring equal and creative participation of all quadruple helix ecosystem sectors and partners.

In terms of the deliverable's contribution towards wider impacts, the following can be considered as supported: New European Bauhaus, Post-Covid Youth Engagement, Civil Role of HEIs and CI in terms of providing in-depth discussion opportunities for stakeholders through roundtables and policy recommendations developed based on the expertise provided by the representatives of the EPIC-WE quadruple helix.

Introduction

Introduction

This deliverable consists of the policy briefs based on the EPIC-WE Project “Task 6.2 – Roundtables for stakeholders and policy development” .

The Quadruple Helix Model, originally conceptualised by Elias Carayannis and David Campbell, was further adapted by Schütz et al. (2019). Such a model is applied in the EPIC-WE proposal and, therefore, is key to the project. For Schütz et al. (2019, p.129), “the four core components of an innovation system – academia, industry, government, and society – are not involved in unidirectional push-pull relationships, but rather in multi-layered, dynamic, bi-directional interaction”. Therefore, the development of policy recommendations and the involvement of actors within the quadruple helix ecosystem are foundational elements in fostering innovation and societal progress. As Etzkowitz and Letdesdorff (2000) highlighted, the quadruple helix model signifies a shift towards collaborative governance structures where academia, industry, government, and civil society engage in synergistic interactions, contributing to knowledge creation and innovation. This collaborative approach is essential for addressing cultural and societal challenges, emphasising the importance of multi-stakeholder joint partnerships in driving sustainable and transformative development. Integrating diverse perspectives and expertise and the development of policy recommendations within the quadruple helix ecosystem and the project can yield more effective and inclusive outcomes while also supporting the project’s core results, objectives, and outcomes, as demonstrated by studies such as Carayannis et al.’s (2009) on innovation ecosystems – which the gaming industry has a strong connection with.

D6.2 has been developed based on the RTs organised in January 2025, combined with other sources (e.g. capacity building sessions and desk research) with the contribution of internal and external stakeholders.

The D6.2 Second Policy Brief is planned to be published on the EPIC-WE Project Website and distributed where convenient and deemed necessary.

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

The flow of the deliverable can be read in different sections: the summary of the first RTs and the policy brief, as well as the pre-, during, and post-organization of the second roundtable, followed by the introduction of the final deliverables.

01

**Summary of the first
EPIC-WE roundtable
and policy brief**

1 Summary of the first EPIC-WE roundtable and policy brief

The first series of roundtables (consisting of a CI, CHI, and HEI roundtable) was organised in October 2023. In advance, materials for the sessions, including general and sector-specific questions and Padlets, were prepared and shared with the participants. After the roundtables were organised, the recordings were transcribed, and the first policy brief was drafted.

Eight recommendations were developed and presented in the first policy brief to address specific challenges and opportunities within the project's framework, reflecting on key focus areas.

D6.1 – First Policy Brief was finalised and submitted in April 2024. The deliverable can be accessed from <https://zenodo.org/records/13882418> and the EPIC-WE Project website <https://epic-we.eu/>

Key Takeaways from Recommendations

Figure 1: Summary of policy recommendations

Key Takeaways from Recommendations

Figure 2: Summary of policy recommendations

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Figure 3: Summary of D6.1

02

Methodology and Preparation

2 Methodology and Preparation

Based on the previous experience and lessons learnt from the first roundtables and policy brief, the following planning was created and followed.

Figure 4: Planning of the roundtables and deliverable

Planning for the deliverable started with reviewing previous work on D6.1, mapping out the differences in execution, and literature review in September and October 2024. The draft structure of the deliverable was planned in October, and as the roundtables were being planned, the task lead started drafting the first version of the report. This included researching and contacting the target groups' representatives to be invited to the sessions and working in collaboration with the project partner institutions. The roundtable was organised on 23.01.2025. After completing roundtables, the task lead compiled the outputs of the sessions and worked on the draft report with other task participants.

03

**Preparatory Work for
Second Roundtables**

3 Preparatory Work for Second Roundtables

3.1 Research Overview

3.1.1 Capacity Building Session on “Policy-Making in CCI’s”

Under T6.3 of the project, a series of webinars and workshops have been organised between November 2024 and February 2025. One of the workshop sessions was “Policy-Making in CCI’s”, organised on 07.02.2025 with the participation of 18 people. The session introduced and explained key aspects of policy-making in CCI’s and provided insight on how initiatives support policy-related activities and efforts through various means (e.g. projects, knowledge transfer, learning platforms, exploitation strategies). Different options for promoting and supporting CCI’s were presented to the participants, highlighting the importance of strategic development, access to finance/funding, and innovation. The key challenges explained during the session were lack of data and metrics, perception of cultural activities, policy priorities, education and awareness, limited access to funding, industry fragmentation, regulatory challenges, intangible assets, and limited market understanding.

3.1.2 Other efforts and resources

There are several initiatives at the EU and local level, with their scopes varying from general support, capacity building, mentoring, funding schemes, etc. Some of these initiatives can be described as follows.

3.1.2.1 European Union Level

1. **Creative Europe:** Creative Europe is the European Commission’s framework programme to support the cultural and creative sectors; with their focus on funding for cross-border cultural cooperation, capacity building, and promotion of European cultural heritage. Creative Europe Desks serve as a national contact point for Creative Europe, providing additional support in advice and promoting funding opportunities.
2. **European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT):** EIT has an established Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC), which focuses on CCI’s in strengthening the competitiveness and integration of CCI’s in Europe.

3. **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF):** ERDF provides financial support for regional and economic development, strengthening regional competitiveness in CClIs.
4. **InvestEU:** InvestEU provides funding to SMEs, including CClIs, with a focus on innovation and sustainability through guarantees and loans. A dedicated instrument, the Culture and Creative Portfolio Guarantee Product provides financial guarantees to financial intermediaries offering loans to creative SMEs. It follows the success of **the Cultural and Creative Sectors Guarantee Facility (CCS GF):** CCS GF was managed by the European Investment Fund (EIF), improving access to finance for cultural and creative industries through a guarantee scheme for financial intermediaries.

3.1.2.2 Cross-Sectoral Programmes and Networks

1. **New European Bauhaus:** New European Bauhaus is an initiative connecting culture, sustainability and innovation to transform living spaces, promoting sustainable design and cultural transformation.
2. **Culture Action Europe (CAE):** CAE is an advocacy network, promoting policies and initiatives that support CClIs.
3. **COSME (2014-2020):** [COSME \(2014-2020\)](#): [The COSME Programme for the Competitiveness of Enterprises and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises \(SMEs\)](#) funds many initiatives that help small businesses access new markets.
4. **Europa Nostra:** A pan-European organisation dedicated to cultural heritage preservation and promoting its role in other sectors, focusing on advocating for the integration of cultural heritage into tourism, education and sustainability initiatives.
5. **Network of European Museum Organizations (NEMO)** NEMO supports museums in collaborating with sectors such as education, technology, and sustainability, focusing on facilitating partnerships between museums and CClIs to innovate and reach wider audiences.
6. **European Creative Hubs Network (ECHN):** ECHN is a network supporting creative hubs to foster innovation, creativity and economic growth; with their focus on knowledge exchange, networking, and scaling creative industries.

3.1.2.3 EU-funded Projects

1. **Creative FLIP**: Pilot project focusing on finance, learning, innovation and patents for CClIs; focusing on capacity building, IP management and access to finance.
2. **Innovation and Creative Solutions for the Sustainable Revitalization of Heritage Areas (INCREAS)**: INCREAS is a Horizon Europe project promoting the innovative use of heritage in CClIs.
3. **Stimulating Performance of Ecosystems in Creative Territories and Regional Actors (SPECTRA)**: Spectra is a Horizon Europe project focusing on key ingredients required to equip the emerging innovator and moderate innovator regions with a more responsive, resilient ecosystem, resulting in enhanced, more inter-connected, diverse, gender-responsive, competitive and sustainable ecosystems in CClIs.
4. **Innovation Policy Platform for the Cultural and Creative Industries (EKIP)**: The EKIP collaborative platform is a Horizon Europe project aiming to create a strong network of networks across CClIs in Europe, focusing on open innovation.
5. **Creative Lenses**: A project in the Creative Europe Programme, implemented from 2015-2019, to explore the issue of sustainability of European arts and cultural institutions, aiming to address how cultural organisations might become more financially sustainable without compromising their missions and values.
6. **YouCount**: The overall objective of the YouCount project is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth across Europe through co-creative youth citizen social science.
7. **YouLeaders**: The YouLeaders project aims to empower and promote the key role of young people as leaders and agents for sustainable development within their communities.
8. **Games for Culture Cluster**: Games for Culture Cluster (GCC) aims to provide evidence and promote the impact that the Games can have in European society.
9. **GAME-ER**: The GAME-ER project aims to explore the emergence, development, and sustainability of video game clusters, with a specific focus on local and regional clusters across Europe. The primary goal is to

generate actionable insights that will help policymakers and industry leaders strengthen or foster the growth of Cultural and Creative Industries (CCI) clusters in their respective regions or cities.

10. **GREAT:** In this project, the aim is to establish ways in which games can be designed to link citizens and policy-makers and produce new knowledge on the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU to benefit society.
11. **i-Game:** i-Game is a European research project aiming to create an accessible open-source game development platform that will facilitate the co-creation of games by diverse actors in an inclusive approach within different ecosystems of cultural and creative sectors and industries.
12. **LoGaCulture:** LoGaCulture brings together European academic leaders in digital locative experiences to explore how a new generation of innovative locative games might benefit European society through its cultural heritage sites.
13. **Mementoes:** The project pairs three museums focused on historical injustices – the USSR’s gulags, wars impacting children, and a mining disaster – with independent game developers. Together, they’ll develop games that allow users to inhabit the perspectives of different groups involved in these events, emphasising the experiences of regular people.
14. **MuseIT:** With the broader ambition of equality, democratisation and social inclusion, MuseIT proposes technologies that facilitate and widen access to cultural assets and help preserve and safeguard cultural heritage in an inclusive way.
15. **FilmEU_RIT:** FILMEU_RIT’s main objective is the capacitation, in Research and Innovation terms, of the individual HEIs that integrate the Alliance via the joint design of strategies and action plans that ensure the transformation of the future European University into an Institution that puts Research and Innovation in the fields of Film and Media Arts at the centre of its activities and operates as a highly valuable critical cultural intermediary.
16. **MESOC:** MESOC (Measuring the Social Dimension of Culture) aim to propose, test and validate an innovative and original approach to measuring the societal value and impacts of culture and cultural policies in Europe.

3.1.3 Key Findings and Research Results

The literature review and research on existing policy briefs highlight some similar key problems described as follows:

3.1.3.1 Challenges accessing consistent and adequate funding

The gaps around this challenge were identified as the need for tailored financing mechanisms, grants, and subsidies that recognise the unique nature of cultural and creative industries. The lack of these might result in limited growth opportunities, reduced innovation and reliance on short-term projects and solutions. Research states that CCI might face a greater uncertainty hazard affecting their business and might be more open to risk averse compared to non-CCI businesses (Fraser S., 2011), resulting in the probability of discouragement and problems in access to finance. In addition, the existing funding schemes and mechanisms usually focus on a fixed-term support, while CHs and LLs could require a sustained support mechanisms and investments for their continuous activities and scaling up; co-financing of funds might be a problem for some CHs and LLs as well. QH actors can face problems in terms of access to funding, with their priorities and focus areas might differ from each other. Funds sometimes expect clear outcomes and results for their contribution, which might raise another problem when it comes to CHs and CIs, as cultural and societal impact might involve qualitative results.

EPIC-WE emphasizes the importance of CHs, LLs and QH actors by setting out principles, protocols and research. Through these efforts, different stakeholders come together to enhance cultural innovation.

Some examples of institutions and initiatives to address this problem can be described as:

Creative Europe¹: Creative Europe provides grants to cultural and creative projects across Europe, including for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in film, music, and heritage; thus, encouraging cross-border collaboration, fostering diversity in cultural outputs and supporting underfunded creators.

UK's Creative Industries Tax Relief²: It offers tax incentives for film, animation, video games, and other creative sectors to encourage investment; helps reduce production costs and supports the creation of local content.

¹ <https://culture.ec.europa.eu/creative-europe>

² <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/corporation-tax-creative-industry-tax-reliefs>

3.1.3.2 Difference between skills taught in academic institutions and industry needs

The gaps around this challenge were identified as the difference between skills taught in and rapidly changing industry needs, especially in emerging fields like gaming, immersive media, cross-sectoral applications, resulting in mismatched links between education institutions and industry requirements. HEIs play a critical role in shaping the future workforce, yet they also face significant challenges in adapting to the rapidly evolving needs of industries such as gaming, immersive media, and cross-sectoral applications. The increasing pace of technological advancements and shifting industry demands require HEIs to continuously update curricula, teaching methodologies, and collaboration models to ensure that graduates are well-prepared for the job market.³ HEIs are key partners in this process, as their expertise in research, pedagogy, and interdisciplinary collaboration is essential for developing educational models. In addition, under the Horizon Europe Programme of the EC, there have been open calls for projects such as “Expanding Academia-Enterprise Collaborations” (HORIZON-EIE-2024-CONNECT-02).

EPIC-WE Project, with its tailored QH model, brings together four different stakeholders to co-create and collaborate by meeting in the middle and providing space for continuous collaboration opportunities, research and transformative partnerships across Europe.

Some examples of institutions and initiatives to address this problem are:

Singapore’s Skills Future Program⁴: This program offers subsidies and training grants for creative professionals to upskill in areas like animation, VR, and multimedia production, allowing professionals to stay competitive in the global market.

EC’s Blueprint for Sectoral Cooperation on Skills⁵: The Blueprint for sectoral cooperation on skills was first introduced by the Skills Agenda for Europe 2016. Since then, the Commission has selected 28 projects under the Erasmus+ programme that are implementing the Blueprint.

³ European Commission: Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, *Understanding the value of a European video games society – Final report*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/332575>

⁴ <https://www.skillsfuture.gov.sg/>

⁵ https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/skills-and-qualifications/working-together/blueprint-sectoral-cooperation-skills_en

3.1.3.3 Fragmented ecosystems with poor collaboration between stakeholders

The gaps around this challenge were identified as the lack of frameworks fostering cross-sectoral cooperation, such as quadruple helix ecosystems, resulting in missed opportunities. QH model tailored for EPIC-WE contributes to bringing together different stakeholders and uniting them in CGJs, research, and joint initiatives with the empowered participation of youth as the fourth helix. It provides internal and external collaboration opportunities for all stakeholders through joint events, capacity building, networking and exploring post-project possibilities across sectors with different institutions involved.

Some examples of institutions and initiatives to address this problem can be described as:

The Quadruple Helix Model: As described in the introduction section of this document, the quadruple helix model encourages collaboration among public institutions, businesses, academia, and civil society to foster innovation in CCI, driving cross-sector initiatives like sustainable design, cultural tourism, co-creation and creative urban planning.

The Netherlands' Top Sector Policy⁶: Top sectors strengthen the economy with innovations by exploiting international opportunities, addressing societal challenges, increasing human capital and investing in scientific research.

3.1.3.4 Geographic disparities, gender inequities, limited inclusion of specific groups

The gaps around this challenge were identified as unequal access to cultural resources, funding and platforms, as well as equal representation and participation in industrial atmospheres, resulting in reduced diversity in expressions and exclusion of underrepresented voices.

Gender Quality Strategy (2020-2025) of the European Commission presents policy objectives and actions towards a gender-equal Europe⁷. In addition to this strategy, with the annual work programmes of Creative Europe, special attention is being paid to gender equality as a driver for creativity, economic growth, and innovation (European Commission, 2024 Report on Gender Equality in the EU⁸). United Nations

⁶ <https://www.nfu.nl/en/themes/research-and-innovation/top-sector-policy>

⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en#gender-equality-strategy-2020-2025

⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en#annual-report-on-gender-equality

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

(UN) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also set out the importance of overcoming gender inequality and focusing on the empowerment of women in their 2030 Agenda as a standalone goal; while stating that the progress is fragile (UN, 2030 Agenda⁹).

“Despite the myths of the CCI as diverse, open and egalitarian, inequalities remain a depressingly persistent feature of most fields.” (Conor, B., Gill, R. & Taylor, S. 2015, p.5).

The Gender Study published by Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH demonstrates the inequalities in the gender dynamics within the CIs and CHIs (e.g. in the U.S film industry, only 15% of directors were women)¹⁰. In addition, according to UNESCO’s “Gender & Creativity: Progress on the Practice” Report, women’s involvement and representation in managerial positions within the CIs remains significantly lower when compared to men¹¹. Furthermore, according to the National Advisory Council on Women and Girls’ “Gender Inequality in the Creative Arts” paper, women account for around a third of the workforce and 60% of part-time positions in Scotland¹².

In addition, a survey conducted by John Voss, focusing on LGBT+ people in the design industry, illustrates several challenges and disparities in the workforce. Another article by John Voss also demonstrates the differences between LGBT+ people in the design industry in terms of duration of involvement in the industry, lower pay rates and feeling less professionally stable¹³.

Different examples from different sectors and regions have inequality in common in terms of ethnicity, gender identity, sexual identity and even age groups.

⁹ <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

¹⁰ <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/cc8cef9784690358cfe4eda77bb85f84-0460012023/original/GIZ-Cultural-and-Creative-Industries-Gender-Study-Executive-Summary.pdf>

¹¹ UNESCO (2021): Gender and creativity: progress on the precipice

¹² <https://www.generationequal.scot/app/uploads/2022/03/NACWG-paper-Gender-inequality-in-creative-industries-FINAL-PAPER-5-August-21.pdf>

¹³ <https://medium.com/queer-design-club/queer-in-the-design-industry-9da266c4d01b>

Figure 5: Employment statistics by gender in design industry¹⁴

Geographical disparities also present a reoccurring problem in participation to cultural activities, in terms of the lack of proximity, as well as financial reasons (European Commission Statistics¹⁵).

As stated in the GA and implemented throughout the project, EPIC-WE Project is committed to supporting inclusion and diversity in all participatory processes. This is performed through multiple channels throughout the project, e.g. YAB members’ distribution, CGJ participants, gender and diversity-sensitive dissemination and communication that prioritize gender inclusivity and equal access. D2.2 “State-of-the-art report” of the project presents an extensive literature review and state-of-the-art and highlights the theme of gender as well as stereotypical gender themes within the industry. The research reveals the topic of gender equality and lack of female participation, not only in game jams, but also in the game development industry. European Commission (2020) also focuses on the topic of gender innovation, and empowerment to underline the importance of empowering women to enhance individual capabilities, as well as the relevance of co-creation and co-design to “empower all citizens” in societal transformation.

In terms of youth empowerment and employment, active engagement of the youth in civic participation is defined as “promoting fully inclusive governance, increasing youth participation in decision-making, ramping up youth employment, engaging

¹⁴ <https://medium.com/queer-design-club/a-read-out-from-the-first-ever-survey-of-lgbtq-people-in-design-33914c05f7b>

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Culture_statistics_-_frequency_and_obstacles_in_participation

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

youth in peacebuilding and gender equality programmes, and ensuring youth are a part of SDG integration, implementation, and monitoring”¹⁶.

Some examples of institutions and initiatives to address this problem are:

Women in Film and Television (WFTV)¹⁷: WFTV advocates for gender parity in creative industries and provides mentoring, networking, and funding opportunities for women aiming to reduce gender disparities in leadership and creative roles.

Canada’s Indigenous Screen Office¹⁸: It supports indigenous storytellers in film, gaming, and multimedia through dedicated funding and training programs.

European Institute for Gender Equality¹⁹: The European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) produces independent research and shares best practice to promote gender equality and eliminate discrimination based on gender.

4 Second Roundtable Session

The session was organised on 23 January 2025 with the participation of 39 people (internal and external, as explained below).

Figure 6: Screenshot from the policy roundtable session - 1

¹⁶ <https://www.undp.org/governance/youth-empowerment>

¹⁷ <https://www.wftv.org.uk/>

¹⁸ <https://iso-bea.ca/>

¹⁹ <https://eige.europa.eu/>

04

**Second Roundtable
Session**

Figure 7: Screenshots from the policy roundtable session - 2

4.1 Internal Participant Profile

AAKS (Filmby Aarhus) provides a collaborative space for creative enterprises, fostering innovation and synergy within the realms of film, gaming, and media production. Positioned as the cornerstone of Aarhus Municipality’s investment in the film and media sector, Filmby Aarhus serves as the epicentre for Jutland’s film, television, and games industry.

ARoS (Aarhus Kunstmuseum) is Scandinavia’s most visited museum and a leading European cultural heritage institution with strong networks in Europe and beyond. ARoS has an ambition to be among the ten most eminent art museums in the world.

AU (Aarhus University) is a public university founded and located in Aarhus, Denmark, in 1928. The Danish School of Education has extensive experience in the fields of Design-Based Research & Design research. AU team holds a strong record and extensive experience in leading international and interdisciplinary funded research projects. Its research team consists of experts in educational design, game jams, co-creation and participatory design and design-based research.

AUAS (Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences) is a lead partner of the Centre of Expertise for Creative Innovation (CoECI), a collaboration between four Amsterdam-based higher education institutions focusing on culture and creative industries. The AUAS’ Visual Methodologies Collective, the research group participating in EPIC-WE, specialises in the developing, applying and testing of visual, digital and participatory methods for social and cultural issues.

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

BS (Battlesheep) is an independent game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, focused on both independent and work-for-hire projects. As an EPIC-WE game industry partner, managed by a team of gaming industry professionals with multi-platform experience, covering PC, Mac, Nintendo Wii, Nintendo DS, iOS, Android, and more, will collaborate in the development of EPIC-WE games, ensuring the production with the quality and reliability necessary for their dissemination to multi-platforms and expected audiences.

CBC (Fonden Creative Business Cup) empowers start-ups in CIs by connecting them to investors and global markets and strengthening their innovative capabilities to the benefit of industry and society. As a platform to pitch ideas, engage with industry leaders, exchange knowledge and share visions on a global stage, CBC brings an exceptionally wide network of CI practitioners.

MEET (MEET Digital Communication) is an International Digital Culture Centre with interconnections to other cultural institutions throughout Europe and various game industries in Italy. MEET, in cooperation with the George Brown College of Toronto, is developing a joint master's in game design where the EPIC-WE results can be integrated, along with various capacity-building activities offered to professionals, artists and designers. In addition, MEET specialises in disseminating digital culture to foster economic growth while increasing opportunity and well-being for the benefit of all citizens.

CMO (Óbidos Municipal Council) is part of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network, involving cultural preservation and creative innovation, including non-formal education, arts, media and history. The preservation and promotion of historical heritage, the support for artistic creation and production, the creation and training of audiences or the democratisation of access to culture are some of its main missions.

DM (Dropstuff Media) specialises in creating interactive public experiences that focus on increasing citizen engagement with arts and culture and facilitating moments of cultural exchange. Additionally, DM has a prominent media profile, presenting at high-profile global events such as SXSW.

KEA European Affairs specialises in public policy design and evaluation, policy advocacy, as well as advisory services to the European institutions in CIs and has a proven track record in managing communication and dissemination activities for large-scale EU research projects.

NISV (The Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision) has extensive expertise in public programming for youth, especially in relation to improving creative and media literacy skills via creative education (WP4). Vocal advocate for strengthening value chains and innovation activities between CHIs and CIs (relevant for WP5-WP6)

through artistic residencies, events for students and artists on possibilities for digital heritage reuse in artistic practices, and research that highlights the impact of creative reuse.

UL (Lusófona University), with 15 Faculties and Schools, was established in 1998, and its core mission is to contribute, through its teaching and research activities, to the scientific, cultural, economic, and social development of Portugal and all countries where the Portuguese language is spoken, while not neglecting its European dimension. Lusófona University has a focus on research and innovation, with experience in international and national funded research projects.

4.2 External Participant Profile

With the contribution of project partners, a detailed list of invitees was prepared, as well as reaching out to other relevant stakeholders. The participant profile for the invitations varied in all focus sectors of the project. As a result, the representatives from the following organisations have participated in the session:

- The Centre for Research & Technology Hellas
- Games for Culture Cluster
- European Students' Association for Cultural Heritage
- Yeditepe University
- CreativeMornings
- Culture Unleashed
- Espas
- Creative Industry Košice
- Studio VRij
- Austrian Commission for UNESCO
- Compendium of Cultural Policies and Trends
- Italian Ministry of Culture
- ARCHES - Advanced Research Centre for Health, Environment and Space
- BDCC Basque District of Culture and Creativity

4.3 Questions & Key Discussions

The following questions were asked and discussed:

1. What is something actionable people can do today to ensure the empowered and active participation of youth in their working area?

2. What role should public-private partnerships play in developing and implementing cultural and creative policies?
3. What role do hackathons or game jams play in generating innovative ideas for cultural programmes or policies?
4. Can you provide concrete examples of successful projects that have empowered stakeholders to co-create cultural content across sectors and/or with youth citizens?
5. Can you provide examples of initiatives or other previous projects that have succeeded in creating impact through games, game-making or culture-making on a European level?
6. How can CIs, CHIs and HEIs better communicate and cooperate to overcome the barriers that prevent them from engaging in new ventures and initiatives that go beyond their current operations in EPIC-WE (and other projects)?
7. Do you know of any programme to support CIs, CHIs and HEIs to better communicate and cooperate on new ventures/initiatives?
8. How can (EU) funding programmes better support cross-sector collaboration between culture, education, and cultural heritage?
9. What mechanisms can be introduced to ensure inclusivity and diversity in policymaking for CIs, HEIs, and CHIs?
10. Younger audiences might not be well connected with cultural heritage (e.g. not visiting heritage sites, not engaging with immaterial heritage). How can policies encourage youth participation and underrepresented groups in cultural creation and innovation?
11. What role should stakeholders play in assessing the effectiveness of implemented policies/programmes?

The key discussions emerging from the asked questions and the contribution of the participants are summarised under different topics as follows:

Youth Engagement, Participation, and Empowerment: The discussions about youth engagement and participation diversified in terms of different opinions. On one side, some participants argued that integrating youth directly in the decision-making processes and existing advisory boards were more efficient and important rather than creating separate advisory boards, while some participants disagreed and preferred to establish separate boards for the youth. Examples from the EPIC-WE Project illustrated how youth advisory boards (YABs) evolved into empowered participation

through making youth equal partners in the QH Cultural Hubs. Peer-to-peer facilitation, mentorship programmes, and project-based learning were identified as essential tools for further empowering youth. Additionally, cultural game jams (CGJs) were highlighted as a dynamic approach to involve youth as empowered participants in cultural heritage through interactive and co-creative activities that enable young people's cultural-creative exploration, experimentation, and innovation.

Public-Private Partnerships in Cultural Policy: Public-private and transformative partnerships were recognised as a key factor in enhancing the impact and effectiveness of cultural initiatives. Public institutions offer ethical guidelines and sustainability measures, while private entities contribute innovation and funding. To maximise these benefits, it was suggested that partnerships should be equal and co-creative rather than hierarchical, avoiding transactional public procurement models that limit creativity. Successful case studies included municipal partnerships with universities and schools, demonstrating how local-level initiatives can foster meaningful engagement between public and private sectors to support cultural projects. One of the EPIC-WE project's (Horizon Europe, 2023–2026) core aims, ambitions, and contributions is to support such a transition into quadruple helix model 3 cultural collaborations and knowledge cultures. EPIC-WE brings together four different sectors to form new transformative partnerships through close co-operation and co-creation: Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), and Youth Citizens (YCs) (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. 2024).

Hackathons and Game Jams: Hackathons and game jams were identified as crucial incubators for creativity, bringing together diverse groups to generate innovative ideas in a short, intensive timeframe. However, their success depends on structured facilitation, mentorship, and clearly defined goals. The EPIC-WE project illustrated how these events can lead to meaningful outcomes when they include a maturation process, ensuring that the results are valued as research and innovation. Additionally, discussions emphasised the importance of game jams as socialisation opportunities, fostering meaningful youth participation and interdisciplinary collaboration that extends beyond the immediate event. Game-making and game-playing carry an immense potential to act as value-carriers and value-creators in European culture and society, harnessing games as and through culture by game-making and game jams as new forms of cultural participation can widen the youth's empowered participation in both cultural heritage and values. Supported by the collaboration within QH partners and including youth as the fourth helix, the co-creation of cultural value and societal change can shape transformations, policies, research and innovation.

Inclusivity and Diversity in Cultural Innovation: While policies advocating for inclusivity and diversity exist, the discussion highlighted that the challenge lies in implementation. Participants emphasised the need to move beyond policy rhetoric

and create tangible opportunities for underrepresented groups to engage with cultural heritage to overcome the barriers and help limit the “monoculture”. The study “The Promised Land? Why Social Inequalities are Systemic in the Creative Industries” presents the networking and work atmosphere in the CIs is disadvantageous for women, people of ethnic minorities and working-class backgrounds, and they find it hard to access the industry (Eikhof, D.R., Warhurts, C. 2013). One proposed approach was to empower local communities to define and support their own cultural heritage initiatives, allowing for a more grassroots-driven cultural landscape. Additionally, ensuring diverse representation in decision-making processes, including funding allocation, was seen as vital to achieving true inclusivity. EPIC-WE commits to implementing strategies to support gender equality, diversity and inclusivity, integrating different demographic profiles in terms of diversity in project activities, CGJs, and the Youth Advisory Board.

Measuring Cultural and Societal Impact: Assessing the impact of cultural initiatives remains a major challenge. Traditional quantitative metrics, such as visitor numbers, are often insufficient in capturing the full extent of cultural engagement. The discussion underscored the importance of qualitative approaches, such as tracking behavioural changes and long-term engagement with cultural activities. Participants called for integrating impact assessment from the outset of projects rather than treating it as an afterthought. A key takeaway was that cultural engagement should be measured using both structured data collection and narrative-based insights to provide a more holistic understanding of its effectiveness.

Overcoming Barriers in Cross-Sectoral Collaboration: One of the key barriers to effective collaboration between creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and academia is the difference in vocabulary and priorities across these sectors. EPIC-WE serves as a space where partners can develop a shared language, methodologies and understanding, making collaboration more seamless. The QH tailored for the project, supported by collaborative efforts and research, contributes to overcoming the mentioned barriers between sectors. This is “materialised” by meeting in the middle as equal partners, progressing with the youth towards cultural innovation through transformative partnerships. Breaking institutional silos and cultivating mutual respect between sectors were highlighted as essential steps in ensuring long-term and meaningful cross-sector partnerships.

05

Policy Recommendations

5 Policy Recommendations

This section provides the recommendations developed based on the roundtable session, involving internal and external partners from CIs, CHIs, HEIs, youth organisations and private institutions with their insights and discussions compiled. Each recommendation addresses a specific challenge and/or gap identified during the session and supported by EPIC-WE's works and efforts. They reflect key focus areas that can be considered guides to adaptable and implementable recommendations in specific contexts. Their interconnection also provides a holistic approach, and it is advised that each recommendation is reviewed separately and together to enhance their impact and effectiveness.

The intersection of creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and higher education institutions drives cultural innovation. However, fragmented collaboration, limited youth engagement, and difficulty assessing impact hinder progress. Strengthening partnerships, fostering inclusivity, and ensuring sustainable funding can enhance their collective contribution to the cultural ecosystem.

General Recommendations

1. **Enhancing Public-Private Collaboration & Partnerships:** *Fragmented ecosystems and collaboration between public and private stakeholders might hinder innovation and sustainability in CIs and CHIs.* Strengthen partnerships between CHIs, HEIs, and private entities to integrate cultural narratives into creative outputs. Public institutions can provide ethical guidelines and stability, while private entities bring innovation and funding. Collaborate with CIs to develop innovative storytelling techniques and digital heritage preservation projects that make cultural heritage more dynamic. Implementing frameworks based on the QH model and establishing national and local councils might encourage collaboration and connect cross-sectoral initiatives.

Strengthening public-private collaboration and partnerships can be achieved by fostering innovation models like the QH model. Ultimately, it is recommended that policies support the establishment of QH CHs and promote equitable, transformative partnerships to drive cultural cooperation and innovation. The EPIC-WE innovation of QH Cultural Hubs directly contributes towards this recommendation (refer to D3.3 foundational principles for QH Cultural Hubs). Core results deliver fundamental principles, shared models, and researched practices of how public-private collaboration and co-creation can be nurtured and enacted through QH partners meeting in the middle to research and innovate together through equal transformative cross-sector partnerships.

2. **Supporting Inclusive, Diverse, Empowered, and Youth-Driven Engagement:** *Geographic disparities, gender inequities, and limited inclusion of marginalised/disadvantaged groups result in reduced diversity in cultural expressions and underrepresentation. Intergenerational, cultural and geographic differences in management approaches might result in reduced interest and active participation of the youth.* Actively involve young people in governance structures by integrating them into decision-making bodies directly to foster intergenerational collaboration and meaningful inclusion. Support policies that amplify diverse voices in cultural production, ensuring representation from different backgrounds and perspectives to avoid homogenisation of content. Encourage young people to actively shape cultural narratives, policies and programs within institutions, ensuring their contributions are valued. Develop structured mentorship programs and internships that allow students to engage with real-world cultural projects, providing practical learning experiences. Create more funding and support mechanisms for women and marginalised/disadvantaged communities; supported by implementing diversity quotas to promote gender parity and inclusion.
3. **Integrating youth as a distinct and active part of the ecosystem** is not just beneficial but essential, as it ensures the sustainability, innovation, and relevance through their fresh perspective, participatory energy and aligns with objectives for inclusivity and co-creation practices. Projects and policies should focus on this topic through structured opportunities such as capacity building, long-term involvement and youth-led initiatives. By integrating elements like these, projects and initiatives can create lasting and meaningful engagement rather than temporary solutions.

Inclusive, diverse, empowered, and youth-driven engagement can be supported by promoting partnerships, projects, and participation aiming for empowered participation and belonging within the cultural domain. Here, the EPIC-WE focus on empowered participation and the inclusion of youth as equal partner in research and innovation within the QH Cultural Hub highlight this dimension in relation to fostering more diverse and inclusive practices and belonging in culture and cultural heritage. Overall, policies nurturing the inclusion of diverse identities, disciplines, and perspectives in culture such as EPIC-WE that stands for 'Empowered Participation in Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments' is recommended.

4. **Sustainable Funding Models:** *Creators and organisations might struggle with consistent and adequate funding due to the absence of tailored financing mechanisms, grants, and subsidies that recognise the unique nature of their sector.* Advocate for flexible funding structures that enable long-term investment in cultural initiatives (e.g. Creative Europe's Guarantee Facility for

the Cultural and Creative Sectors²⁰). Reducing reliance on short-term grants can create stability for cultural projects and organisations, developing national-level funding schemes to prioritise long-term projects and sustainable business models. Expand funding programmes to include microgrants tailored for independent creators and start-ups. Work towards establishing tax incentives to reduce financial burdens on small creative initiatives.

The QH model in EPIC-WE gives the utmost importance to equal and balanced partnerships of the actors for co-creation and co-operation in research and innovation. The added fourth helix actor is considered an integral part of the system, ensuring their access to finance and funding.

5. **Impact Assessment Mechanisms:** Utilize context-tailored assessment methods to measure cultural projects' effectiveness, focusing on long-term cultural and social impact beyond economic returns.

It is important to foreground assessment methods that align with cultural and artistic values rather than solely relying on traditional quantitative and qualitative metrics. In this regard, it emphasises methodologies that capture the nuanced impact to reflect the lived experiences, cultural contributions, and societal value of EPIC-WE. To achieve this, using narrative-based evaluations, participatory and co-creative assessments enable a deeper understanding of impact assessment not in just numerical terms but through meaningful, context-sensitive measures that correspond to the project's cultural background and objectives. The impact assessment of the project focuses on diverse metrics such as skill, playfulness, fun, empowerment, inclusion, knowledge, co-creation and collaboration to provide a compelling narrative and assessment that meets the creative nature and values of the project.

6. **Leveraging Digital and Interactive Media:** *Insufficient infrastructure for digital transformation, including digitising cultural heritage and adopting emerging technologies, might result in lagging behind technological advancements.* On the national level, implement strategies to preserve and make cultural assets accessible.

Open access to publications and outputs within projects such as EPIC-WE serves as a fundamental space for further research and innovation. The project provides open access to all CGJ kits, capacity-building events, testimonials, research publications, games created during CGJs, interviews and many more. Communication and dissemination efforts also contribute to public access to all documentation and material produced to ensure maximised knowledge transfer.

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/memo_16_2346

These can be accessed from:

- Project website: <https://epic-we.eu/>
- Resource website: <https://epic-we.au.dk/games>
- Media centre: https://mycreativenetworks.com/topics/45642/media_center

- 7. Localised and Glocalised Community Engagement:** Encourage community-driven funding models where citizens can participate in cultural projects that reflect their values and heritage interests, increasing public investment in cultural sustainability. This approach empowers local communities to take an active role in shaping cultural landscapes, ensuring the funded projects and initiatives resonate with local identities and historical narratives. Governments can facilitate these initiatives by developing participatory budgeting platforms, and match-funding schemes in which public funds supplement community contributions.

EPIC-WE's interventions provide a model for using game-making as a scalable tool for youth. Glocal exchange helps CGJ participants learn how to interact with other communities and cultures, supporting young people in getting an understanding of how games, cultural heritage and creativity can be harnessed to positively contribute to social causes and empower them. Cultural exchanges through glocal CGJs facilitate productive interaction between different cultures. Supported by the QH model, CGJs in local and glocal sites contribute to the youth's game-making practices and co-creation across sectors in Europe to foster cultural exchange, inclusion, and cohesion.

QH CHs serve as a novel approach to collaborative ecosystems that enable HEIs, CHIs, CIs and youth to engage in co-creative processes and cultural heritage. The project emphasises the importance of local communities while fostering cultural exchange and innovation, ensuring cross-cultural collaborations and game-making processes with local, regional, national and European perspectives while continuously influencing the local cultural hubs (quoted from D3.3 Report).

- 8. Practice-Based Learning Models, Innovation & Bridging the Gap:** Bridging the gap between HEIs, CHIs and CIs might be achieved through various means and methods. To make sure that each partner is equally represented and benefits from the efforts, fostering cross-sector collaboration, enhancing subsidies and support for the adoption of innovative tools and methods, supporting research, and joint programmes and initiatives are highly crucial for the cross-sectoral transformative partnerships and collaboration; which helps each sector understand the needs in other sectors.

The EPIC-WE focus on enacting collaborative, co-creative partnerships between the sectors through meetings in the middle – each sector is an equal partner in research, innovation, and culture. Each contributes with unique values, skills, methods, and practices. Only through joining forces in the middle are the sectors able to work towards cross-sector transformations and innovations that will actually succeed in ‘bridging the gap’ and creating sustainable and valuable models for all QH partners (including youth/students).

9. **Public Accessibility:** Ensure that research findings are translated into accessible and applicable formats for policy-makers, practitioners, and the public. This enables different QH actors to value the research practices more and encourages them to discover opportunities to combine research with practical aspects of their industries and work.

As previously explained in discussion points, open access to research, publications and documentation to the public is essential to enable seamless knowledge exchange within QH model actors. Removing barriers to information, this practice fosters collaboration, innovation, and inclusive development and ensures that findings can be accessible and actionable for all stakeholders. The transparency of outcomes and research results strengthens cross-sectoral partnerships, accelerates societal impact and development, and enhances co-creation and development of knowledge, resulting in sustainable and equitable progress across domains.

10. **Expanding Roles:** *Despite their value-added and influence, cultural hubs (CHs) and living labs (LLs) might not be systematically included in policy discussions, thus limiting their influence and knowledge transfer on shaping cultural and digital transformation.* Incorporate these institutions into consultation processes to ensure the roots and practicalities of cultural innovation are correctly reflected in policy-making. Support policy experimentation initiatives where CHs and LLs can test innovative governance models within their communities and influence community-led cultural strategies and policies. This would also support enhanced public-private collaborations and partnerships.

To address the inclusion of CHs and LLs for enhancing their influence and knowledge, the incorporation of the QH and CH model of EPIC-WE as a framework ensures their integration at the policy level, where policy-makers may actively engage and participate in the ecosystem. Uniting these institutions into policy-making processes helps ground policy-making in the realities of cultural innovation, where CHs and LLs can support the innovative models. This approach not only strengthens community-led cultural strategies

06

Next Roundtables

but also enhances public-private collaborations and partnerships, ensuring a more inclusive, effective and resilient cultural policies that are responsive to challenges and opportunities.

- 11. Encouraging Sustainability:** *Establishing and supporting sustainable practices for environmental concerns, economic instability and inequities in resource access is a vital priority in various sectors.* Encourage green transition initiatives and CIs and CHIs (e.g. eco-friendly game development practices and game jams, sustainable cultural events, eco-friendly and/or upcycled material usage). Develop sustainability guidelines for these sectors. Support green certification programmes for CIs that implement sustainable practices. Support cross-sectoral partnerships between CIs and CHIs and green tech to drive innovation in environmental-friendly productions in these sectors (e.g. Creative Climate Leadership Programme²¹, Greening in European HEIs²², Green Education²³, Green Deal Roadmap²⁴) through impact, creativity, and resilience.

Using EPIC-WE's QH framework for cultural innovation and integrating sustainability into the practice through the QH approach could foster eco-conscious cultural and creative production and research by promoting sustainable development. By embedding sustainability into cultural innovation processes, EPIC-WE and other initiatives might use their platform and network to highlight the need for sustainable practices and environmentally conscious approaches and help promoting and raising awareness to integrate sustainable practices into cultural innovation. Integration of sustainability can also facilitate cross-sectoral dialogue between industries, encouraging knowledge exchange and sustainability-driven cultural policies, aligning with broader EU and/or UN goals for sustainability.

6 Next Roundtables

The concluding RT will be organized as a panel in conjunction with the final conference, on the European level, in M36 of the project.

²¹ <https://www.creativeclimateleadership.com/>

²² <https://www.eua.eu/publications/reports/greening-in-european-higher-education-institutions.html>

²³ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/focus-topics/green-education/about-green-education>

²⁴ <https://www.eua.eu/publications/reports/a-green-deal-roadmap-for-universities.html>

07

Conclusion

7 Conclusion

The RT session served as a dynamic platform for in-depth discussions, generating valuable insights that will directly inform both policy recommendations and broader strategic directions. The diverse composition of participants—spanning internal and external stakeholders from various sectors and regions—greatly enriched the discourse, fostering meaningful knowledge transfer and cross-sectoral learning. This diversity not only amplified the depth of perspectives but also reinforced the essential role of inclusive dialogue in driving co-creation, value-making, and collaborative knowledge production.

Throughout the session, a wide range of perspectives and challenges were explored, further strengthened by the sharing of external resources, relevant projects, and publications. The active engagement of stakeholders facilitated a comprehensive understanding of key obstacles, gaps, and areas for improvement, particularly in relation to the active participation of youth as the fourth actor in the QH model. Their role in shaping the future of cultural innovation and transformative change emerged as a critical focal point, emphasizing the need for more inclusive and youth-driven innovation ecosystems.

As highlighted in the key discussion topics, the way forward requires a strong commitment to fundamental principles such as transparent communication, cross-sectoral collaboration, inclusion, diversity, empowerment, and sustained cooperation. Ultimately, this RT session not only provided a space for open dialogue but also actively contributed to the broader objectives of the EPIC-WE project. It facilitated connections between stakeholders, introduced new initiatives, and laid the groundwork for future collaborations that will further drive cultural innovation and systemic transformation. The discussions held here are not just reflections—they are actionable starting points for shaping more inclusive, sustainable, and forward-thinking cultural policies and practices.

Bibliography and Appendices

8 Bibliography

Carayannis, E., & Campbell, D. (2009). 'Mode 3' and 'Quadruple Helix': Toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem. *International Journal of Technology Management - INT J TECHNOL MANAGE*. 46. 10.1504/IJTM.2009.023374.

Clissmann, I., Straus, M., Ilijas, T., Pecency, U.S., Kalin, T. 2023 Insights into European Cultural Heritage Sector

Conor, B., Gill, R. & Taylor, S. (2015). Gender and creative labour. *The Sociological Review*, 63(1_supp), pp. 1-22. doi: 10.1111/1467-954x.12237

Cultural and creative industries: Breaking Barriers, Driving Change: Unveiling Gender Dynamics in the Cultural and Creative Industries. (2023). <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/cc8cef9784690358cfe4eda77bb85f84-0460012023/original/GIZ-Cultural-and-Creative-Industries-Gender-Study-Executive-Summary.pdf>

Eikhof, D. R. and C. Warhurst (2013). The Promised Land?: Why social inequalities are systemic in the creative industries. *Employee Relations*, 35(5), 495-508.

Etzkowitz, H., Leydesdorff, L. (2000). The dynamics of innovation: From National Systems and “Mode 2” to a Triple Helix of University-Industry-Government Relations, *Volume 29, Issue 2*, 109-123.

European Commission, 2019. Skills Mismatch & Productivity in the EU. https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-07/dp100_en.pdf

European Commission, 2023. The European Media Industry Outlook. file:///Users/belitayaydin/Downloads/The_European_Media_Industry_Outlook_gSlquDKUttimCSzo8gO0dhvYuWI_95874.pdf

European Commission, 2024 Report on Gender Equality in the EU. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en#annual-report-on-gender-equality

European Commission: Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Understanding the value of a European video games society – Final report, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/332575>

European Commission. (2018). A new European agenda for culture. https://culture.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2020-08/swd-2018-167-new-european-agenda-for-culture_en.pdf

European Commission. Culture Statistics – Frequency and obstacle in participation.

WP6 – D6.2. Second Policy Brief

European Parliament, 2023. Developing the video games and e-sports sector in the EU.

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/749808/EPRS_BRI%282023%29749808_EN.pdf

Fraser, S. and IFF Research (2011). Access to Finance for Creative Industry Businesses. Report for BIS and DCMS.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Culture_statistics_-_frequency_and_obstacles_in_participation

<https://tourism4-0.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Heritage-report.pdf>

Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024). Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 57(2), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2024.2384722>

Schütz, F., Heidingsfelder, M. L., & Schraudner, M. (2019). Co-shaping the Future in Quadruple Helix Innovation Systems: Uncovering Public Preferences toward Participatory Research and Innovation. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 5(2), 128-146.

UN, 2030 Agenda. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

UNCTAD, 2024. Digital Economy Report 2024: Shaping and Environmentally Sustainable and Inclusive Digital Future

9 Appendices

1. SWOT Analysis – HEI, CI, CHI

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